

Response to the reviewers (GIGA-D-18-00483)

We thank the reviewers and editors for their critical assessment of our work initially, providing feedback and accepting our manuscript for publication. In the following we address their concerns point by point.

Reviewer 1

Reviewer Point P 1.1 — - p.2: The first paragraph: The term ‘WMS’ is used before introducing ‘Workflow Management System’ that is introduced in the fourth paragraph in p.2.

Response: [We have provided the full form and introduced the abbreviation to be used later.](#)

Editor notes: As a CWL paper it would be good to put any workflows highlighted here into the CWL viewer tool, include permalinks for any figures using the workflows, and sending us RO bundles for them to archive in GigaDB.

Response: [We have added the GigaDB link to Section “Availability of supporting data and materials”.](#) This link contains snapshot of the data and methods utilised in this study.

[We have also provided additional cwl viewer links as suggested by GigaScience editor.](#)